

RULE BOOK - ATP -

ALTERNATIVE TRANSIENT PROGRAM

RB-02A-39.PDF

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CAUE - COMITE ARGENTINO DE USUARIOS DE EMTP - ATP

<http://iitree.ing.unlp.edu.ar/estudios/caue/index.htm>

Buenos Aires / diciembre 2001

II-A-39 HARMONIC FREQUENCY SCAN

Harmonic Frequency Scan (HFS) performs a sequence of phasor solutions for Type 14 voltage and/or current sources of various frequencies, amplitudes and angles specified by the user. HFS is the ATP option for harmonic analysis in electrical networks.

Data for HFS runs can be divided into 6 classes

- 1 - Special Request entries and Miscellaneous Constants
- 2 - \$PARAMETER entries
- 3 - BRANCH data including requests for frequency dependent elements
- 4 - Special output request
- 5 - Source specifications
- 6 - Specification of frequency dependence of elements

II-A-39-1 Special Requests

Class 1 data includes as a minimum the two Special Request entries of

BEGIN NEW DATA CASE and HARMONIC FREQUENCY SCAN as shown below

1										2										3										4													
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0	1	2	3	4
B E G I N N E W D A T A C A S E																																											
H A R M O N I C F R E Q U E N C Y S C A N																																											

The user can enter optional Special Requests such as listed in Section 2A of the Rule Book. Typical entries may be POWER FREQUENCY or PRINTED NUMBER WIDTH etc. The user has to verify that such Special Request entries do not conflict with the process of the HARMONIC FREQUENCY SCAN..

An optional but important Special Request with harmonic frequency scan is the use of the Pocket Calculator for varying the value of an element (R-L-C) as a function of frequency (harmonic order). This option is introduced by the Special Request POCKET CALCULATOR VARIES PARAMETERS (PCVP) in conjunction with the \$PARAMETER request as explained below.

1										2										3										4										5													
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0	1	2	3	4
C																				I 6										I 6																							
P O C K E T C A L C U L A T O R V A R I E S P A R A M E T E R S																				M A X K N T										I O P C V P																							

In the general purpose use of PCVP (see Rule Book Section I-L) the value of MAXKNT sets the number of passes the user wants to make with varying.

parameters. For such study MAXKNT is an arbitrary number demanded by the user. For HFS studies MAXKNT should be set to zero in column 48, as MAXKNT is internally set to the number of different frequency sources specified by the user.

IOPCVP = 0 generates a .LIS file with a full output for each pass which may be required for some general purpose applications with PCVP, but it is wasteful for HFS. With IOPCVP = 1, the .LIS file contains the tabulation of output variables for each frequency specified and the new parameter values for each frequency as changed by the KNT dependent formulas in \$PARAMETER.

In the latest (July 1999) version of TPBIG the PCVP request can be deleted.

The above Special requests are followed by two MISCELLANEOUS DATA These are the same Miscellaneous Data described in Section 2B of the Rule book, but are repeated here to indicate that recommended entries for an HFS run.

First Miscellaneous Data record

1									2									3									4										
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
E 8 . 0									E 8 . 0									E 8 . 0									E 8 . 0										
DEL T A T									T M A X									X O P T									C O P T										

The value of DELTAT and TMAX has no meaning for HFS, but cannot be left blank. Enter 1.0 for both constants. XOPT and COPT have the same meaning as described in Section II-8.

Second Miscellaneous Data record

1									2									3									4										
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
I 8									I 8									I 8									I 8										
I O U T									I P L O T									K S S O U T																			

5												6													
9	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0	1	2	3	4
I 8												I 8													
I C A T																									

Enter "1" for both IOUT and IPLOT to have outputs in the .LIS file for each frequency specified. KSSOUT =1 will generate a detailed phasor output for each frequency, resulting in a large volume of output, which for the usual HFS is not warranted. KSSOUT = 0 is the recommended usage. If plotting of results is required enter ICAT = 1, which will be the general case for HFS runs.

II-A-39-2 \$PARAMETER Specification

Class 2 data is required if the PCVP option is used for user defined frequency dependence of R-L-C elements. Rules for using the PCVP in conjunction with \$PARAMETER is described in detail in Section I-L of the Rule Book. The HFS use is shown here on a simple example. In HFS applications, the ATP constant **KNT** which in the general case is the sequence counter of the sequence number of passes in a systematic or statistical run, is internally made equal to the harmonic order **h** = frequency/power frequency. The frequency dependence of an element has to be defined by the user as a function of KNT being the same as the function of frequency.

Let BUSHFS be the name of a node to which a frequency dependent impedance RHFS + j XHFS is connected. With the harmonic order **h** equal to **KNT**, let

$$\begin{aligned} \text{RHFS} &= 0.35 * \text{KNT} ** 2 \text{ and} \\ \text{XHFS} &= 1.21 * (1 + \text{KNT} ** 0.4) \end{aligned}$$

To enter these elements the user will have entered the PCVP request among the Class 1 data as outlined above. Following the Miscellaneous data the following shows the data entry for \$PARAMETER.

1										2										3										4									
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0
\$PARAMETER																																							
RHFS __ = 0.3 * KNT ** 2.0																																							
XHFS __ = 1.21 * (1.0 + KNT ** 0.4)																																							
BLANK card ends \$PARAMETER definitions																																							

In the BRANCH data the above frequency dependent elements are entered as follows

1									2									3									4																					
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
BUSHFS																		RHFS _ _									XHFS _ _																					

Note the use of under scores to form six character names compulsory in transferring data from the \$PARAMETER section to BRANCH data.

The \$PARAMETER section uses free format Fortran statements with floating point numbers. Integers are not allowed. The user should carefully study the Rule Book section on PCVP application. (Section I-L)

II-A-39-3 Frequency Dependent Elements

Class 3 HFS data is the same as the regular data for time domain runs. As HFS is a sequence of phasor solutions, nonlinearities cannot be represented. Nonlinear elements will be treated the same way as they are treated in the phasor solution of a time domain run.

Frequency Dependent R-L-C Elements

Linear frequency dependence of an R – L - C element can be modeled as described in Section II-A-39-6. User defined non-linear frequency dependence of an R – L- C element has to modeled using the PCVP option. An example is shown in Section II-A-39-7 - Simulation Samples

The CIGRE Load Model

A frequency dependent distribution system load model was developed for HFS, but it is usable for FS and time domain simulations. After the originators of the model, it is called the CIGRE model, and characterized by three constants A, B, and C. The user enters the load MW, MVAR and kV and the three constants, ATP calculates the load impedance for the harmonic orders. The C.I.G.R.E. recommended constants are A= 0.073, B= 6.7 and C=0.74. The model is valid for harmonic orders of 5 and higher and may yield incorrect reactive absorption at the fundamental frequency. This is usually not a problem, but the user should be aware of it and compensate for it if required. The changing of the recommended constants will change the overall frequency dependence of the model, and should be carefully analyzed by the user. For details of the model see C.I.G.R.E. Publication Electra Vol. 71, 1981.

The format for entering a single phase CIGRE load at a bus BUSL:

1										2										3										4																			
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0										
C																														E 1 6 . 2																			
										<LOAD> CIGRE A , B , C																				A																			
C										A 6										A 6																				E 1 6 . 0									
										BUSL										<LOAD>																				VOLT									

Continued

5										6										7										8									
3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0		
E 1 6 . 0																				E 1 6 . 2																			
B																				C																			
E 1 6 . 0																				E 1 6 . 0																			
PLOAD																				QLOAD																			

The constants A, B, C are defaulted to 0.073, 6.7 and 0.74 respectively, or entered by the user.

1. VLOAD is r.m.s. voltage across the load
2. PLOAD is the active power absorbed by the load
3. QLOAD is the reactive power absorbed by the load

VLOAD, PLOAD and QLOAD has to be specified in units consistent with the source specifications. E.g. if the source voltages are in volts, VLOAD is in volts, PLOAD is Watts and QLOAD is in VARs

For three phase loads the data input can be simplified as follows Let the three phase load be connected to nodes BUSLA, BUSLB, BUSLC

1										2										3										4																													
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0																				
C																														E 1 6 . 2																													
										<LOAD> CIGRE A , B , C																				A																													
C										A 6										A 6										A 6										E 1 6 . 2																			
										BUSLA										<LOAD3										BUSLB										BUSLC										VOLT									

Continued

5										6										7										8									
3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0		
E 1 6 . 2																				E 1 6 . 2																			
B																				C																			
E 1 6 . 0																				E 1 6 . 0																			
PLOAD																				QLOAD																			

VOLT, PLOAD AND QLOAD are single phase quantities

Induction Motor HFS Model

There is no built-in induction HFS induction motor model at the present time. In most cases it will be sufficient to use the locked rotor power frequency locked rotor impedance of the motor. Should a more sophisticated model be required, the PCVP option may be used to for generating the frequency dependent characteristic of the rotor. An example in Section II-A-39-7 – Simulation Samples

Synchronous Machine HFS Model

There is special synchronous machine HFS model. It is generally recommended to use the negative sequence impedance

II-A-39-4 Output Requests

The old restriction of only node voltage outputs with FREQUENCY SCAN has been removed. Both node and branch voltage currents can be output the usual way with column 80 entries of 1, 2, or 3, which is available for both FS and HFS. In the old FS output node voltages were recorded with their magnitudes, angles, and real and imaginary components. This has been changed to only magnitudes being monitored as the default option. For HFS, the user can request the additional output of the angle of the variable by inserting a POLAR OUTPUT VARIABLES request after the end of SWITCH data as follows:

1										2										3										4																			
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0
BLANK Ending SWITCHes																																																	
POLAR OUTPUT VARIABLES																																																	
C f o l l o w e D b y S O U R C E d a t a																																																	
14										B U S A										e t c .																													

II-A-39-5 Sources

Only Type 14 sources are available in HFS due to the fact that HFS is a sequence of phasor solutions. Source frequencies can be given in Hertz **Hz** or in the harmonic order **h**. The two type of source frequency specification cannot be mixed. There has to be at least one source with the power frequency equal to the default power frequency or the power frequency as modified at the top of the data file. If sources are specified in terms of the harmonic order **h**, there has to be at least one source with $h = 1$. ATP calculates internally the frequency in Hz corresponding to **h**. Sources can be entered in any order, they are sorted internally. The general format for entering sources is:

1										2										3										4									
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0
I 2		A 6								I 2		E 1 0 . 6								E 1 0 . 6								E 1 0 . 6											
1 4		NAME								J		AMPL PL .								FREQ . o r H								ANGLE											

NAME the name of the source bus
J blank for a voltage source and -1 for a current source
AMPLITUDE the peak voltage or current magnitude
FREQ the source frequency in Hz
h the harmonic order in per unit
ANGLE the source voltage or current angle in degrees
 Columns 41 to 80 must be blank

II-A-39-6 Elements with Linear Frequency Dependence

An R -L - C element with linear frequency dependence can be specified by entering the value at a specified higher frequency. ATP will make a linear interpolation at any given frequency (harmonic order). The records to enter this specification follow the last source specification as shown in the following format

1										2										3										4																			
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8												
1		BUSA								- 1		1 0 0 0 . 0								5 0 .								1 2 0 .																					
C l a s t s o u r c e																																																	
C																														E 1 0 . 1																			
NEXT FREQUENCY FOR SERIES RLC																														FREQU																			
C		A 6								A 6								E 6 . 2								E 6 . 2								E 6 . 2															
		BUS A 1								BUS A 2								R								L								C															
		BUS B 1								BUS B 2								R								R								R															
C r e a t e r f o r n e w f r e q u e n c y a n d b r a n c h e s																																																	
BLANK e n d i n g f r e q u e n c y d e p e n d e n c e																																																	

FREQ is the elevated frequency at which the new value of the element is specified
NAME1 NAME2 is the name of the branch to which an R -L - C element is connected

R, L, C are the elements in branch NAME1 to NAME2

There can be several sets of frequency dependence specification of R - L - C elements

II-A-39-7 HFS Examples

Example #1

Linear frequency dependence of R L and CIGRE load model

```

BEGIN NEW DATA CASE
POWER FREQUENCY, 50.0
HARMONIC FREQUENCY SCAN
C DELTAT      TMAX      XOPT
   1          1          50.
C   IOUT      IPLOT                                ICAT
   1          1                                1
C   10 km cable
-1SRCA  LOADA          1.280 0.152 0.408 10.0
-2SRCB  LOADB          0.164 .0987 0.408 10.0
-3SRCC  LOADC
C   frequency dependent impedance
C           R      X      = 0.3 +j0.6 at 500 Hz
   LOADA LODA          0.1  0.3
   LOADB LODB          0.1  0.3
   LOADC LODC          0.1  0.3
C   frequency dependent CIGRE type load  kV, 4.8 MW, 2.4 MVAR
   <LOAD> CIGRE A,B,C          0.073          2.0          0.74
   LODA <LOAD3LODB LODC      5780.0          1600000.      80000.  1
C   branch to the converter
   LOADA CONVA          0.1
   LOADB CONVB          0.1
   LOADC CONVC          0.1
BLANK end of BRANCH data
BLANK end of SWITCH data
POLAR OUTPUT VARIABLES
C   amplitude Hz or h      angle
C 10 kV 50 Hz voltage source
14SRCA      8150.00      1.      0.
14SRCB      8150.00      1.      240.
14SRCC      8150.00      1.      120.
C   assume 3% negative sequence voltage at source
14SRCA      245.00      2.      10.
14SRCB      245.00      2.      130.
14SRCC      245.00      2.      250.
C   harmonic sources at converter
14CONVA -1      60.0      1.0      10.0
14CONVB -1      60.0      1.0      250.0
14CONVC -1      60.0      1.0      130.0
C           5th
14CONVA -1      12.0      5.0      10.00
14CONVB -1      12.0      5.0      130.00
14CONVC -1      12.0      5.0      250.00
C           7th
14CONVA -1      8.0      7.0      10.00
14CONVB -1      8.0      7.0      250.00
14CONVC -1      8.0      7.0      130.00
C           11th
14CONVA -1      5.0      11.0      10.00
14CONVB -1      5.0      11.0      130.00
14CONVC -1      5.0      11.0      250.00
BLANK ending SOURCES
NEXT FREQUENCY FOR SERIES RLC          500. { Elevated frequency for interpolation
   LOADA LODA          0.3  0.6
   LOADB LODB          0.3  0.6
   LOADC LODC          0.3  0.6
BLANK card ending F-dependent series R-L-C branches
   LOADA LOADB LOADC
BLANK end of OUTPUT data
BLANK end of PLOT data
BEGIN NEW DATA CASE
BLANK

```

-

Example #2 Demonstrates the use of the PCVP

```

BEGIN NEW DATA CASE
C this data file demonstrates the simple HFS modeling of an induction
C motor with only one rotor circuit. The model is created by the
C POCKET CALCULATOR VARIES PARAMETERS option
POWER FREQUENCY, 50.0
HARMONIC FREQUENCY SCAN
POCKET CALCULATOR VARIES PARAMETERS          0      1
C DELTAT      TMAX      XOPT
   0.001      -1.0      50.
      1          1          1
$PARAMETER
C demonstrates the uses of a frequency dependence induction motor
C locked rotor impedance. Only the R component is frequency dependent
C Motor : 3ph, 0.38 kV, 550 kVA, slip = 0.8%, locked rotor reactance = 27%
C rrotor = slip * V(kV)**2 / MVA
C rrmot = 0.008 * (0.38**2 / .5 5) = 0.0021 ohm/ph
C the locked rotor inductance assuming xd' = 27%
C Xlmot = 0.27 * (0.38**2 / .5 5) = 0.00709 ohm/ph
C note the underscores making up the 6 char. names, only for those variables
C which are passed to the network data
C the constant KNT is made equal to h in ATP
C $$ signifies an intermediate variable
XLMOT_ = 0.27 * 0.38**2/0.55
SLIP = 0.008 $$
RMOTS = 0.008 * 0.38**2/0.55 $$
C the following expression is MOD(h,3)
HMOD = ( KNT - 3.0 * TRUNC (KNT/3.0)) $$
C test for the sequence number
Z = (-1.0) ** HMOD $$
HS1 = (KNT + Z) $$
C HS is the "harmonic slip"
HS = (HS1 + SLIP)/KNT $$
RMOT_ = RMOTS/HS
BLANK card ends $PARAMETER definitions
C Source bus 10.0 kV 95 MVA
51SRCA BSA .30000 3.1000
52SRCB BSB .01100 1.0528
53SRCC BSC
C BSA to BSMA is a measuring switch
C 10.0 kV cable equivalent to plant bus 2.0 km
-1BSMA TR10A 0.38 0.410 0.30 2.0
-2BSMB TR10B 0.38 0.410 0.30 2.0
-3BSMC TR10C
C
C Transformer 1000 kVA
C x = 6.5% x = 10**2/1.00 = 100.0 ohm * 0.065 = 6.50 ohm
C imag = 1.5 A , r = 0.5 ohm/ph
C
TRANSFORMER          3.0 40.0 AX
      9999
1TR10A TR10B .800 19.00 10.0
2LS3A GRS .001 .0001 .220
TRANSFORMER AX AY
1TR10B TR10C
2LS3B GRS
TRANSFORMER AX AZ
1TR10C TR10A
2LS3C GRS
GRS 1.0
C line to converter
LS3A CONVA 0.001 0.020
LS3B CONVB 0.001 0.020
LS3C CONVC 0.001 0.020
C *****
C Induction motor 500 kW
C *****
C induction motor, 500 kW, 380 V, modeled by locked rotor reactance
C -----
LS3A MOTA RMOT_XLMOT_
LS3B MOTB RMOT_XLMOT_

```

1

```

LS3C  MOTC          RMOT__XLMOT_
MOTA  MOTSA        .00001   { source separation
MOTB  MOTSB        .00001
MOTC  MOTSC        .00001
C
BLANK end of BRANCH data -----|
C SWITCHES
C          measure current in 10 kV feeder
BSA   BSMA         -1.0    10.0          1
BSB   BSMB         -1.0    10.0
BSC   BSMC         -1.0    10.0
C
BLANK end of SWITCH data -----|
POLAR OUTPUT VARIABLES
C power frequency voltage source 10 kV 3 ph
14SRCA      8150.00      1.      0.
14SRCB      8150.00      1.     240.
14SRCC      8150.00      1.     120.
C
C Voltage source for the induction motor
14MOTSA     307.50      1.     -85.
14MOTSB     307.50      1.     155.
14MOTSC     307.50      1.      35.
C
C current injection at converter bus CONVA,B,C
C 500 kVA fundamental 933 A r.m.s. 1315 A peak
14CONVA -1  1315.0      1.0   -170.00
14CONVB -1  1315.0      1.0    70.00
14CONVC -1  1315.0      1.0   -50.00
C harmonic sources
14CONVA -1  1.000      3.0   -170.00
14CONVB -1  1.000      3.0    70.00
14CONVC -1  1.000      3.0   -50.00
C
14CONVA -1  1.000      4.0   -170.00
14CONVB -1  1.000      4.0    70.00
14CONVC -1  1.000      4.0   -50.00
C
14CONVA -1  150.00     5.0   -310.00
14CONVB -1  150.00     5.0   -190.00
14CONVC -1  150.00     5.0    -70.00
C
14CONVA -1  108.00     7.0   -110.00
14CONVB -1  108.00     7.0   -230.00
14CONVC -1  108.00     7.0   -350.00
C
14CONVA -1  70.00     11.0  -250.00
14CONVB -1  70.00     11.0  -130.00
14CONVC -1  70.00     11.0   -10.00
C
BLANK card ending all source cards
BLANK ending frequency dependent cards
TC10A TC10B TC10C
LS3A  LS3B  LS3C
BSA   BSB   BSC
BLANK ending OUTPUT requests.
BLANK ends plot cards
BLANK
BEGIN NEW DATA CASE
BLANK
-

```